

JAVASCRIPT DA O'ZGARUVCHILAR. MA'LUMOTLAR TIPI.

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JavaScript, dinamik tili sifatida, o'zgaruvchilarni va ularning ma'lumotlar tipini yaratish va ishlatish uchun juda yaxshi qo'llab-quvvatlanadi. Bu tezisda, biz JavaScript'dagi o'zgaruvchilar va ma'lumotlar tipi haqidagi tushunchalarni o'rganamiz.

O'zgaruvchilar

JavaScript'da o'zgaruvchilarni yaratish uchun var, let va const kalit so'zlari ishlatiladi:

```
var x = 10;
```

```
let y = 20;
```

```
const z = 30;
```

var: Eski o'zgaruvchi yaratish usuli. O'zgaruvchining global yoki funksiya bo'ylab qamroq hosil qiladi.

let: Blok bo'ylab qamroq hosil qiladi va o'zgaruvchining qiymatini o'zgartirishga ruxsat beradi.

const: Blok bo'ylab qamroq hosil qiladi, lekin o'zgaruvchining qiymatini o'zgartirish mumkin emas.

Ma'lumotlar Tipi

JavaScript'da 7 ta asosiy ma'lumotlar tipi mavjud:

Number: Butun va o'nlik sonlar uchun ishlatiladi. Masalan, 42, 3.14 va NaN (not a number).

BigInt: Katta butun sonlar uchun ishlatiladi. Masalan, 9007199254740991n.

String: Matnlar uchun ishlatiladi. Masalan, "Hello, World!", 'JavaScript' va `Template literals`.

Boolean: Mantiqiy qiymatlar uchun ishlatiladi. true yoki false bo'lishi mumkin.

Null: Bo'sh qiymatni bildiradi. Faqatgina null qiymati bo'ladi.

Undefined: O'zgaruvchining qiymati belgilanmaganligini bildiradi. Faqatgina undefined qiymati bo'ladi.

Object: Ma'lumotlar to'plami yoki qobiliyatlar to'plami sifatida ishlatiladi. {} yoki new Object() orqali yaratiladi.

Number

JavaScript'da sonlar uchun faqatgina bitta ma'lumotlar tipi mavjud - Number. Bu, butun va o'nlik sonlarni o'z ichiga oladi. Sonlarni ishlatishda maxsus funksiyalar ham mavjud, masalan:

```
Math.sqrt(9).
```

BigInt

BigInt tipi, katta butun sonlarni saqlash uchun mo'ljallangan. Ushbu tipning qiymatlarini yaratish uchun n belgisi ishlatiladi: const bigInt = 1234567890123456789012345678901234567890n.

String

Matnlar String tipida saqlanadi. Matnlarni ishlatishda maxsus funksiyalar va operatorlar mavjud, masalan: str.length, str.concat(str2), str.charAt(index) va boshqalar.

Boolean

Mantiqiy qiymatlar Boolean tipida saqlanadi. Ular, shartli operatorlar va mantiqiy funksiyalar ishlatilganda yaratilishi mumkin.

Null va Undefined

null va undefined qiymatlar, o'zgaruvchining qiymatining yo'q ekanligini bildiradi. null - bu o'zgaruvchining qiymati yo'q, lekin bu qiymat dasturchi tomonidan belgilangan. undefined - bu o'zgaruvchining qiymati hali belgilanmagan.

Object

Object tipi, JavaScript'dagi eng keng tarqalgan ma'lumotlar tipi. Ular, ma'lumotlar to'plamini yoki qobiliyatlar to'plamini ifodalash uchun ishlatiladi.

Ob'ekt qiymatlarini yaratish va ishlatish uchun usullar:

```
const person = {
  firstName: "John",
  lastName: "Doe",
  age: 30,
  greet: function() {
    return "Hello, " + this.firstName + " " + this.lastName;
  }
};
```

```
console.log(person.firstName); // "John"
console.log(person.greet()); // "Hello, John Doe"
```

Ma'lumotlar tipini aniqlash va o'zgartirish

JavaScript dinamik tili sifatida, o'zgaruvchilar ma'lumotlar tipini o'zgartirishga ruxsat beradi. Ma'lumotlar tipini aniqlash uchun typeof operatori ishlatiladi:

```
console.log(typeof 42); // "number"
console.log(typeof "Hello, World!"); // "string"
console.log(typeof { firstName: "John", lastName: "Doe" }); // "object"
```

Ma'lumotlar tipini o'zgartirish uchun turli usullar ishlatiladi. Masalan, sonni matnga o'zgartirish uchun toString() funksiyasi yoki matnni songa o'zgartirish uchun parseInt() va parseFloat() funksiyalari:

```
const num = 42;
const str = num.toString();
console.log(str); // "42"
const str2 = "3.14";
const num2 = parseFloat(str2);
console.log(num2); // 3.14
```

Xulosa

Ushbu tezisda, JavaScript'dagi o'zgaruvchilar va ma'lumotlar tipi haqidagi asosiy tushunchalar va usullar ko'rib chiqildi. JavaScript, o'zgaruvchilarni yaratish va ma'lumotlarni saqlash uchun juda keng qo'llab-quvvatlangan, dinamik tildir. Bu, dasturlashni qulay va samarali qiladi, lekin ma'lumotlar tipi bilan ishlashda ehtiyot bo'lish talab qilinadi.

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